

DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTION OF RUST FUNGI CAUSING PLANT DISEASES IN SWAT DISTRICT, KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA (KP), PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT: Two short field survey were made during 2015 in Swat valley, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan for rust diseases of wild plants. In all 4 genera of rust fungi with 8 species parasitic, on 5 different families of plant Hosts were collected and identified, from which 9 species of rust fungi are addition to the fungal flora of Swat valley. Most of the rust fungi were collected from herbaceous wild plants. This study suggests further exploration of the area of rust disease in order to access the diversity of these fungi. Previously 58 species of 7 genera rust belonging to 26 families of hosts are described from Swat valley. After this study, the species level of rust fungi in swat valley become 65 and generic level upto 8.

Key words: Rust flora, Swat district, Diversty and Distribution

INTRODUCTION

District Swat is a part of the high altitude Hindu Kush Himalaya (HKH) region of Pakistan comprising a diverse set of biophysical, ecological and socio-economic characteristics [1]. It is bounded by the district Kohistan and Shangla in the East; the district Buner in south-east; district Malakand in south-west; district Dir in west and district Chitral in north. The area is situated between 35° 23' 0" N Latitude to 72° 11' 0" E Longitude. The altitude of Swat from starting at Saidu Shrif is 970 meters while at Kalam altitude is 2300 meters [2]. In all, floristic composition comprised of 209 species of vascular plants belonging to 167 genera and 75 families [3]. The rust fungi belongs to the order Uredinales of class Basidiomycotes and comprise a large group of obligate biotrophic parasites. They cause rusty pustular outgrowths on different plant parts especially leaves and stem of the wide range of host plants including ferns, conifers and wild and cultivated flowering plants [4]. Plants and rust biotrophs are known to have specific relationships. The host-parasite association between plants and rust is an outcome of a long evolutionary process of continuous mutual adaptation. [5]. Rust fungi are among the most economically important pathogens of many native and cultivated plants. However, they typically cause only minor damage to a population of wild host plants in an area belonging to their natural range of distribution [6]. Malik and Khan started the description of fungal flora of Swat and then there is major contribution by Ahmad, Ono and Kakishma. From Swat district 7 genera and about 56 species of rust fungi have been described [7-22].

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The rust sori were seen under stereo-microscope (MEIJI TECHNO, EMZ-5TR, Japan) and made slide in lactic acid for microscopic feature. For their microscopic features

include shape, size, ornamentation of teliospores, urediniospores, pedicel, germ pore were studied. Line diagrams were made with the help of LUCIDA (Ernst Leitz Wetzlar, Germany). With the help of Biological microscope (Labomed CXR II, Labo America, Inc. USA) measurements of morpho-anatomical features (teliospores, urediniospores, pedicel, germ pore) were presented from at least 20 measurements made with an ocular micrometer (LOMO Filar Eyepiece Micrometer AM9-2 15x microscope ZEISS) in 40x or 100x oil immersion objective. For photography microscopic camera (HDCE-5X digital camera 5.0MP) was used.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Phragmidium papillatum Dietel, Hedwigia 29: 25 (1890) SPERMOGONIA, AECIA and TELIA not found. UREDINIA mostly hypophyllous on leaves, or on the veins and petioles, bright yellow to orange, scattered, rounded or oblong. UREDINIOSPORES globose to sub-globose, yellowish orange, 18-26 × 20-23µm, wall 1.88-4 µm thick, 1-2 germ pores, obscure, echinulate to verrucose with hyaline pedicel.

Material examined On *Potentilla gerardiana* Lindl., with II stage, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar, at 1421 m. a. s. l, 1st May, 2015. MU# 04.

Phragmidium papillatum, previously reported on *Potentilla nepalensis* from Swat and on *Potentilla gerardiana* from Azad Jammu and Kashmir [19,[23].

Phragmidium papillatum is a new record for Swat district, KP, Pakistan.

FIGS. A-E: *Phragmidium papillatum* (A). Infected host plant *Potentilla gerardiana*, (B-E). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 0.1 cm, B-D= 12 µm, E= 5.3 µm.

FIG. A: Lucida drawings of *Phragmidium papillatum* (A). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 6.2 µm.

Puccinia conyzae Henn., Hedwigia 35(5): 239 (1896). SPERMOGONIA, AECIA and TELIA not found. UREDINIA mostly amphigenous, on leaves, light brown to dark brown, scattered, rounded or oblong. UREDINIOSPORES globose to ellipsoidal, moderate yellowish brown, 13-18 × 20-33 µm, wall 1-2 µm thick, obscure, echinulate, with broken pedicels, 1-2 (mostly 2) germ pores, equatorial.

Material examined On *Conyza ambigua* DC., with II stage, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar at 1421 m. a. s. l, 1st May, 2015. MU#05.

Puccinia conyzae previously reported on *Baccharis* sp, *Conyza* sp and *Conyza triplinervia* from Brazil, on *Conyza viscidula* from Taiwan [24].

Puccinia conyzae is a new record for Pakistan.

FIGS. A-I: *Puccinia conyzae* (A-B). Infected host plant, *Conyza ambigua*, (C-I). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 0.72 cm, B= 0.5 cm, C= 8.47 µm, D= 22.5 µm, E= 7.71 µm, F-I= 16.87 µm.

FIG. A: Lucida drawings of *Puccinia conyzae* (A). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 5.4 µm.

Puccinia virgata Ellis & Everh., Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad. 45: 154 (1893)

SPERMOGONIA and AECIA unknown. UREDINIA intermixed with telia. UREDINIOSPORES globose to ovoid, 24.5-31 × 28-35 µm, wall 2-3 µm thick, light brown, echinulate, 1-2 germ pores, equatorial to sub-equatorial; paraphyses cinnamon brown to chestnut brown, capitate, apical wall 2-4 µm thick, apex 2-22 µm wide, upto 60 µm in length. TELIA hypophylous, dark brown to blakish brown. TELIOSPORES bicelled, 19-28 × 36-50 µm, wall 2-4.5 µm thick, apex rounded to conical, 3.3-7 µm thick, pedicel hyaline to cinnamon brown, mostly broken, 5.4-9.6 µm wide.

Material examined On *Panicum antidotale* Retz., with II & III stages, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar at 1421 m. a. s. l, 1st May, 2015. MU# 08.

Puccinia virgata is a new record from Swat, KP, Pakistan, previously it is reported on *Panicum antidotale* from Azad Jammu and Kashmir and Bara gali, KP, Pakistan [25] [26].

Puccinia virgata is a new record for Swat district, KP, Pakistan.

FIGS. A-E: *Puccinia virgata* (A). Infected host plant *Panicum antidotale*, (B). Paraphyses, (C). Urediniospore and teliospore, (D). Teliospores, I. Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 2.5 cm, B= 15 µm, C= 12.28 µm, D= 19.54 µm, E= 19.68 µm.

FIGS. A-C: Lucida drawings of *Puccinia virgata* (A). Teliospores, (B). Paraphyses, (C). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 8.95 µm, B= 9.23 µm, C= 9.84 µm.

Puccinia graminis* subsp. *graminis Pers., Neues Mag. Bot. 1: 118 (1794)

SPERMOGONIA and AECIA not found. UREDINIA present on abaxial surface, scattered, light brown in color. UREDINIOSPORES globose to sub globose and ellipsoidal, 20.5-27 × 28.5-35.5 µm; wall 1.5-3.3 µm thick, light yellow to brown in color, echinulate, germ pores 1-2 equatorial to sub-equatorial. TELIA abaxial, scattered, dark brown in color. TELIOSPORES, 17-30 × 46-70 µm; wall 1.5-3.5 µm thick, smooth, clavate or ellipsoid, upper cell rounded, lower cell elliptical, apical thickness 6-13 µm, pedicel hyaline to yellowish brown, 6.5-10 µm wide and upto 50 µm long.

Material examined On *Bromus japonicus*. Thunb., with II & III stage, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar at 1421 m. a. s. l, 1st May, 2015. MU# 09.

Puccinia graminis subsp. *Graminis* is previously reported on *Bromus japonicus* Thunb., from Swat state, Miana [8,9,14,15,16,20.

FIGS. A-D: *Puccinia graminis* subsp. *Graminis* (A). Infected host plant *Bromus japonicus*, (B-D). Teliospores with urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 1.25 cm, B= 82.25 µm, C= 29 µm, D= 36.25 µm.

FIG. A-B: Lucida drawings of *Puccinia graminis* subsp. *Graminis* (A). Teliospores. (B). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 13.48 µm, B= 10 µm.

Caecoma rosicola Afshan, Niazi & Khalid, Mycotaxon 120: 243 (2012)
 SPERMOGONIA, UREDINIA and TELIA not found.
 AECIA hypophyllous on leaves or petioles, mostly on the veins, petioles, branches and fruits, causing malformation, yellowish orange to bright orange, scattered, paraphyses absent. AECIOSPORES globose to sub-globose or ellipsoidal to ovoid, wall hyaline with yellowish orange contents, echinulate to verrucose, 30-43 × 35-48 µm, wall 6-11 µm thick, 1-4 germ pores, mostly equatorial, obscure.

Material examined On *Rosa*. L., with I stage, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar at 1421 m. a. s. l, 1st May, 2015. MU# 11.

Caecoma rosicola is previously reported on *Rosa webbiana* from Khanspur, KP, Pakistan [27].

Caecoma rosicola is new record from Swat ditrict, KP, Pakistan.

FIGS. A-D: *Caecoma rosicola* (A). Infected host plant, *Rosa* sp., (B-D). Aeciospores. Scale bar for A= 0.8 cm, B= 51.87 µm, C= 34.58 µm, D= 16.6 µm.

FIG. A: Lucida drawing of *Caecoma rosicola* (A). Aeciospores. Scale bar for A= 9.22 µm.

Puccinia clavata P. Syd. & Syd., Monogr. Uredin. (Lipsiae) 1(3): 545 (1903) [1904]

SPERMOGONIA and AECIA and UREDINIA not found. TELIA hypophyllous, scattered, dark brown to black in color. TELIOSPORES are two celled, ovoid to ellipsoidal, 25-39 × 36-46 µm; wall 2-4 µm thick, prominent apical germ pore, pedicel hyaline, 3-6µm thick and up to 41 µm long.

Material examined On *Clematis montana* D. Don., with III stage, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar at 1421 m. a. s. l, 15th July, 2015. MU# 12.

Puccinia clavata is a new record from Swat district, previously it has been reported on *Clematis* sp from Balauchistan [9].

Puccinia clavata is a new record from Swat district, KP, Pakistan.

FIGS. A-E: *Puccinia clavata* (A). Infected host plant *Clematis montana*, (B-E). Teliospores. Scale bar for A= 1.66 cm, B= 13.66 µm, C= 20.6 µm, D= 16.4 µm, E= 24.1 µm.

A

FIG. A: Lucida drawings of *Puccinia clavata* (A). Teliospores. Scale bar for A= 13.66 µm.

Puccinia menthae Pers., Syn. Meth. Fung. (Göttingen) 1: 227 (1801)
 SPERMOGONIA and AECIA not found. TELIA absent. UREDINIA hypophyllous, brown, rounded, scattered. UREDINIOSPORES globose to obovoid or ellipsoid, 18.5-22.52 × 21.95-27.52 µm, light yellow to light orange, wall 1-2 µm thick, echinulate, hyaline to light yellow; germ pores 1-2, equatorial; pedicel hyaline.

Material examined On *Nepeta* L., with II stage, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar at 1421 m. a. s. l, 15th July 2015. MU# 23.

Puccinia menthae has been reported on *Mentha sylvestris* L. from Quetta, Chillianwala, Mingora, Poonch, Kaghan valley, Naran, Murree hill and Peshawar; on *Origanum vulgare* L. from Kaghan valley, Naran, Sharan and Changa gali; on *Calamintha umbrosa* and *C. clinopodium* from Kaghan. Batakundi, Changla Gali, Swat, Kalam and Naran; on *Nepeta* sp from Kaghan valley [8] [9]. On *Mentha logifolia* from Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Neelam valley, Sharda [28]. *Puccinia menthae* is a new record on *Nepeta* sp from Swat district, KP, Pakistan.

FIGS. A-E: *Puccinia menthae* (A-B). Infected host plant *Nepeta* sp, (C-E). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 1 cm, B= 0.31mm, C= 9.89 µm, D= 11.77 µm, E= 11.77 µm.

A

FIG. A: Lucida drawings of *Puccinia menthae* (A). Urediniospores. Scale bar for A= 7.27 µm.

Uromyces dactylidis G.H. Oth, Mitt. Naturf. Ges. Bern 469-496: 85 (1861)
 SPERMOGONIA and AECIA not seen. UREDINIA absent. TELIA on abaxial surface, mostly amphigenous, dark brown to blackish brown, subepidermal. TELIOSPORES ellipsoid to broadly ellipsoid or obovoid, 16.42-24.54 × 20.51-30.51 µm, wall 1.47-2.93 µm thick at side, 3.72-5.09 µm thick apically, brown to chestnut, brown, smooth, apex mostly rounded, sometimes truncate, pedicel hyaline to yellowish, collapsing, 6.17-8.67 in width and up to 15 µm long.

Material examined On *Agrostis gigantea* Roth. With III stage, Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Swat district, Kozshawar at 1421 m. a. s. l, 15th July 2015. MU# 24.

Uromyces dactylidis is a new record for Swat, previously it has been reported on *Agrostis gentia* from Khanspur, KP, Pakistan [29].

Uromyces dactylidis is a new record from Swat district, KP, Pakistan.

FIGS. A-E: *Uromyces dactylidis* (A-B). Infected host plant *Agrostis gigantea*, (C-E). Teliospore. Scale bar for A= 1.72 cm, B= 0.33 mm, C= 11.05 µm, D= 12.75 µm, E= 9.08 µm.

FIGS. A: Lucida drawings of *Uromyces dactylidis* (A).
Teliospores. Scale bar for A= 6.37 μ m.

CONCLUSION

Swat district have thick vegetation including economically important plants but it is not explored area with respect to data of rust disease. This study provide the diversity and distribution of rust flora of Swat District, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan. This data will be used for further research related to biocontrol of wild plants and for further study.

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LIST OF FUNGAL FLORA OF SWAT

Sr.	Pathogenic Fungus	Host Plant	Host Plant Family	References
1	<i>Gymnosporangium clavariiforme</i>	<i>Cotoneaster integerrimus</i>	Rosaceae	[8][9]
2	<i>Phragmidium bulbosum</i>	<i>Rubus pungens</i>	Rosaceae	[21]
3	<i>Phragmidium papillatum</i>	<i>Potentilla nepalensis</i>	Rosaceae	[8][9][19]
4	<i>Phragmidium rosae-moschatae</i>	<i>Rosa brunonii</i> <i>Rosa moschata</i> <i>Rosa centifolia</i> <i>Rosa lacerans</i> <i>Rosa webbiana</i>	Rosaceae	[19]
5	<i>Phragmidium shogranense</i>	<i>Rubus sp</i>	Rosaceae	[8][9]
6	<i>Phragmidium tuberculatum</i>	<i>Rosa webbiana</i>	Rosaceae	[19][20]
7	<i>Puccinia absinthii</i>	<i>Artemisia persica</i> <i>Artemisia parviflora</i>	Asteraceae	[19]
8	<i>Puccinia angelicae</i>	<i>Angelica glauca</i>	Apiaceae	[8][9]
9	<i>Puccinia barclayi</i>	<i>Polygonum amplexicaule</i>	Polygonaceae	[8][9]
10	<i>Puccinia bistortae</i>	<i>Polygonum affine</i>	Polygonaceae	[19]
11	<i>Puccinia brachypodii</i> var. <i>poae-nemoralis</i>	<i>Poa sterilis</i>	Poaceae	[20]
12	<i>Puccinia calcitrapae</i>	<i>Carduus edelbergii</i> <i>Cirsium argyranthum</i>	Asteraceae	[8][9][19][20]
13	<i>Puccinia caricina</i>	<i>Carex sp</i>	Cyperaceae	[19]
14	<i>Puccinia carthami</i>	<i>Carthamus oxyacantha</i> <i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>	Asteraceae	[8][9][16]
15	<i>Puccinia chrysanthemi</i>	<i>Chrysanthemum pyrethroides</i>	Asteraceae	[19]
16	<i>Puccinia chrysopogoni</i>	<i>Chrysopogon echinulatus</i>	Poaceae	[10]
17	<i>Puccinia caricina</i>	<i>Circaea pricei</i>	Onagraceae	[18][19][20]
18	<i>Puccinia coronata</i>	<i>Agrostis sp</i> <i>Rhamnus virgata</i>	Poaceae Rhamnaceae	[7][8][9] [12][13]
19	<i>Puccinia echinopis</i>	<i>Echinops cornigerus</i>	Asteraceae	[8][9]
20	<i>Puccinia graminis</i>	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> <i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Poaceae	[8][9]
21	<i>Puccinia hieracii</i>	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	Asteraceae	[8][9][14][15]
22	<i>Puccinia hieracii</i> var. <i>hieracii</i>	<i>Cichorium intybus</i> <i>Picris hieracioides</i>	Asteraceae	[19][12]
23	<i>Puccinia hultenii</i>	<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	Polygonaceae	[17][19]
24	<i>Puccinia komarovii</i>	<i>Impatiens racemosa</i> <i>Impatiens radiata</i>	Balsaminaceae	[17][19]
25	<i>Puccinia leveillei</i>	<i>Geranium 3999alcate3999</i> <i>Geranium rectum</i>	Geraniaceae	[8][9]
26	<i>Puccinia melanocephala</i>	<i>Aquilegia fragrans</i>	Ranunculaceae	[19]
27	<i>Puccinia menthae</i>	<i>Mentha longifolia</i> <i>Origanum vulgare</i> <i>Calamintha umbrosa</i> <i>Nepeta sp</i> <i>Clinopodium vulgare</i>	Lamiaceae	[18][19][20]
28	<i>Puccinia nepalensis</i>	<i>Rumex nepalensis</i>	Polygonaceae	[8][9][12][19]
29	<i>Puccinia nitidula</i>	<i>Bistorta amplexicaulis</i> <i>Bistorta vivipara</i>	Polygonaceae	[17][19]
30	<i>Puccinia oenanthes-stoloniferae</i>	<i>Oenanthe javanica</i>	Apiaceae	[8][9]
31	<i>Puccinia oxyriae</i>	<i>Oxyria digyna</i>	Polygonaceae	[10][12]
32	<i>Puccinia pimpinellae</i>	<i>Pimpinella diversifolia</i>	Apiaceae	[8][9][19]
33	<i>Puccinia polygoni-amphibii</i>	<i>Polygonum pterocarpum</i>	Polygonaceae	[8][9]
34	<i>Puccinia prenanthis-purpureae</i>	<i>Prenanthes brunoniana</i>	Asteraceae	[18][19]

35	<i>Puccinia recondita</i>	<i>Aquilegia fragrans</i>	Ranunculaceae	[19]
36	<i>Puccinia ribis</i>	<i>Ribes glaciale</i>	Grossulariaceae	[7][8][9]
37	<i>Puccinia sibirica</i>	<i>Aconogonum molle</i>	Polygonaceae	[19]
38	<i>Puccinia sorghi</i>	<i>Zea mays</i>	Poaceae	[19][14][15]
39	<i>Puccinia swertiae</i>	<i>Swertia petiolata</i>	Gentianaceae	[8][9]
40	<i>Puccinia violae</i>	<i>Viola canescens</i> <i>Viola betonicifolia</i> <i>Viola serpens</i>	Violaceae	[8][9][12][19]
41	<i>Uromyces appendiculatus</i>	<i>Lablab purpureus</i>	Fabaceae	[8][9]
42	<i>Uromyces behenis</i>	<i>Silene vulgaris</i>	Caryophyllaceae	[19]
43	<i>Uromyces capitatus</i>	<i>Desmodium tiliifolium</i>	Leguminosae	[8][9]
44	<i>Uromyces ciceris-soongaricae</i>	<i>Cicer songaricum</i>	Leguminosae	[10]
45	<i>Uromyces clignyi</i>	<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i>	Poaceae	[8][9]
46	<i>Uromyces geranii</i>	<i>Geranium aconitifolium</i> <i>Geranium donianum</i>	Geraniaceae	[8][9][19]
47	<i>Uromyces polygoni-avicularis</i>	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i> <i>Polygonum viviparum</i>	Polygonaceae	[7][8][9][10][14][15][19]
48	<i>Uromyces valerianae-wallichii</i>	<i>Valeriana jatamansi</i>	Valerianaceae	[18][19]
49	<i>Coleosporium datiscaae</i>	<i>Datisca cannabina</i>	Datisceae	[11]
50	<i>Coleosporium lycopodis</i>	<i>Campanula cashmeriana</i>	Campanulaceae	[8][9][12]
51	<i>Coleosporium pseudocampanulae</i>	<i>Campanula pallida</i>	Campanulaceae	[19]
52	<i>Hyalopsora polypodii</i>	<i>Adiantum capillus-veneris</i> <i>Cystopteris fragilis</i>	Adiantaceae Woodsiaceae	[8][9][10][19]
53	<i>Melampsora epitea</i>	<i>Salix sp.</i> <i>Salix tetrasperma</i>	Salicaceae	[8][9][15]
54	<i>Melampsora euphorbiae</i>	<i>Euphorbia wallichii</i>	Euphorbiaceae	[17]
55	<i>Melampsora euphorbiae-gerardiana</i>	<i>Euphorbia 4000alcate</i> <i>Euphorbia sp</i> <i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i>	Euphorbiaceae	[8][9]
56	<i>Melampsora salicis-albae</i>	<i>Salix acmophylla</i>	Salicaceae	[8][9]
57	<i>Puccinia striiformis</i> var. <i>striiformis</i>	<i>Lolium persicum</i>	Poaceae	[30]
58	<i>Puccinia coronata</i> var. <i>himalensis</i>	<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	Poaceae	[30]